

Resilient Coasts Survey Results

St Andrews

Resilient Coasts: Optimising Co-Benefit Solutions (Co-Opt) is an interdisciplinary research project involving the University of St Andrews, University of Liverpool, National Oceanography Centre and Cranfield University.

The postal survey aimed to explore the perceptions of coastal flood risk management and various coastal schemes in the UK. Co-Opt project aims to highlight what is required to support the implementation of green/nature-based solutions for flood risk management.

126 participants from St Andrews (21% response rate)

56% 42%

31% aged 18-44

50% aged 45-74

19% aged 75 and above

Mean distance to the coast =
0.96 km

Mean distance to rivers=
0.78 km

19%
experienced
flooding and/or
erosion

62%
have noticed
coastal change

83%
concerned about
climate change

36%
have not heard
about nature-
based solutions

31%
would accept
managed realignment
if people are not
displaced

Top 3 preferred coastal flood risk protection strategies:

1 Dune restoration

“It's most natural and least intrusive”

2 A mix of options

“A mix of options to match the complex and composite issues that need to be addressed”

3 Restoration/recreation of natural habitats

“Restoration and recreation of natural ecosystems as it will protect the coastline from both erosion and flooding as well as encourage habitats and biodiversity, while also being a reasonable costing solution”

76%
not confident they can influence local decisions

29%
do not think the local authority is prepared well for coastal change

Trust rate among St Andrews respondents (1=do not trust at all, 5=trust completely)

More info about the project:
<https://projects.noc.ac.uk/co-opt/>